

GEOSCANNING METHOD

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Abstract

Has been developed a fundamentally new prospecting method of various ore mineralization at any depth - geoscanning method (multipoint measurement).

It based on other principles then all existing prospecting methods, hasn't analogy and gives result when other methods don't works (particularly at depth).

The main point of the method is a search of hidden and overlapped abyssal mineral resources.

For a number of ore fields in Uzbekistan and Russia this forecast produced excellent and already confirmed results.

Accuracy of forecast is very high - up to detection of ore bodies.

To make forecasts using geoscanning method only topographical map and outlines and/or points on reference mineralization are required.

The geoscanning method is accurate, effective and not laborious. It can be applied in complex with other prospecting methods.

Using known ore as a sample in the geoscanning method, the mineral resources hidden at any depth can be determined locally, precisely and in detail. The parameters of discovered resources (depth, content and etc.) will correspond to the sample.

Topographical maps of scales 1:200000-1:100000 well works for discovery ore fields and large deposits, of scales 1:50000-1:25000 – for deposits and theirs sectors, of scales 1:10000-1:2000 – for discovery concrete ore bodies.

The method is quite applicable to the prospecting for oil and gas.

1. Geoscanning method - extraction of depth ore signal using physicogeometrical parameters of relief

This method is developed to deep determine hidden or overlapped mineralization of different mineral types and parameters (reserves (contents), depth of different ore elements); the method is remarkable for its precision and forecasting locality.

Method allows increasing forecasting effectiveness at the cost of expected reserves and proved reserves parameters approximation; considerably reduce geological risk, temporal log and capital investments for exploration works while implementing mining projects.

Main point of geoscanning method (multipoint measurement) is to determine mineralization (both hidden and overlapped) at a depth using well-defined geometric parameters - first partial derivatives of relief as set of elevations and reference mineralization. Precision and generality of relief parameters measurement in every point of area creates a huge amount of "samples" (in this case "samples" are geometric properties of the space) that determine contours of specific ore bodies almost identically.

To make forecasts using geoscanning method only topographical map and information on reference mineralization are required, absolute coordinates x , y , z of topographical maps and content of ore elements are not necessary.

Innovational geoscanning method tested at: gold-silvers deposits of Chadak ore field, Upper Karakya area (Arabulak and Bachtavak-II deposits) – East Uzbekistan; gold-silver Mardjanbulak ore field and adjoining areas – West Uzbekistan; copper-nickel-platinum Kingash deposit and adjoining areas (Russian Federation – to order corporation “Nornickel”; near gold Belaya Gora deposit (Russian Federation) and etc. – where showed good results.

2. Method description

Experience of the last decades shows that reserves of easily detectable and open from the surface deposits are practically utilized. It is clear that their essential increase is possible at the cost of exploration of considerable hidden and overlapped shallow beds, which are economically efficient for mining projects.

On the other hand, imperfections of traditional geological-structural, geophysical, geochemical and other methods of in depth exploration associated with principal inaccuracy and impossibility of mass measurements of definable parameters are well known.

While implementing mining projects the choice is either high accuracy and mass measurement of definable parameters or ineffectiveness of specific large-scale local forecast (scale of ore bodies) which is lower than 3% in exploration of hidden and overlapped mineralization. In both cases it involves rise in prices of expensive exploration works .

2.1. Theoretical justification of the method

Solution of this problem on a rigorous quantitative level is application of geoscanning method (extraction of depth ore signal using physicogeometrical parameters of relief) which is remarkable for its higher accuracy, generality and cost efficiency .

Geological meaning of this method is that substance (specific chemical elements, their associations) as mineralized state has specific values of certain determined geometric parameters - first partial derivatives of relief as set of elevations. In other words, information about perturbing ore substance is immediately reflected by relevant geometric properties of surface relief as a bedding interface.

Note: Finding the first partial derivatives can be viewed, from another point of view, as integration of the relief parameters, because the operations of differentiation and integration are interrelated.

The principle of the idea is very simple - it is that mass, space and time are interconnected. We select the reference mineralization and thus equate time to unity, then the geometric parameters of space (relief) will be directly related to mass, i.e. in our case with ore mineralization. All physics is based on this principle.

2.2. Method technology

Specific methods of computation based on differential geometry and (modern) abstract algebra with the most general mathematical theories are used in calculations. Method technology comes to the following:

1. Direct problem is solved - first partial derivatives of relief as set of elevations in each point of area (or using quite dense grid) are defined within investigated (reference) area.

Integrated values of relief parameters in auxiliary value space for "ore" and "non-ore" are always located in certain dissimilar, spatially disconnected and symmetric regions with insignificant number of matches, i.e. located in opposite phases. They form typical patterns with regular symmetry elements and developed scale effects.

2. Final is the solution of inverse problem - relevant processing of relief parameters on unexplored area and ore signals extraction (vertical projection of probable mineralization on surface), which combination is easily interpreted as ore bodies (pic.1).

Results of discharge of forecast - forecasting layouts (a vertical projections of forecasting mineralization with parameters (content, reserves, depth and etc.) of reference ore mineralization on specified area, for specified gradations reference mineralization, with specified accuracy, perspective sectors in form of layers on given topographical or geological map and short explanatory note.

3. Forecasting examples

Effectiveness and accuracy of the forecast is confirmed by specific examples comparing prognostic layout and available actual data. Moreover the author originally knew only the topographic base and reference ore mineralization.

The first forecast was made for one of Russian mining companies. As reference ore mineralization is taken deposit more than in 100 km from forecasting area, in similar geological and geomorphological situation. Non-singular mineralization within the most explored sites containing more than # at the depth up to #m and supported by results of heavy mining and drilling works and generally coinciding with contours of commercial mineralization is taken as "ore" standard.

State survey map with 1:50000 scale was used for research.

Company asks for non- mention region and deposit's name so in present time on given objects conduct actives prospecting work.

Figure 1. The first forecast (it better to increase).

Selected 7 perspectives sectors, one of them coincides with well-known deposit and 3 another coincides with geochemical and geophysical anomalies, results of geological researches, sampling data, and selected as high-priority.

On the east of forecasting area, along river valley, were took symbolic significances of isolines because of absence of relief isolines.

Forecasting objects enough locals. In more detail (including on level of ore bodies) in this scale topographical map "ore signal" select it is impossible, need it scale as minimum 1:25000. The points of relief measures (accuracy) arranges every 120 m. In all on area come out more then 10000 reliefs "samples".

In general on reference deposit predominates isometric relief forms. This one can to expect on forecasting area, this is a sort ore guide.

Forecasting maps constructed in form bubbles diagrams of Excel (coordinates X, Y and significances in form of size bubbles). Diagrams are "living", they can be changed. With operating formulas easy to change a visualization of forecasting maps (when it changes parameters it can considerable change because of scales effects).

In general come out what "ore signal" in average correspond to reference deposit (not much big blues bubbles on diagrams with high significances correspondence to reference ore mineralization). But much reds bubbles (low level correspondence to reference ore mineralization), although they enough big. (Look legend).

When conducting prospecting should be considered that each part of the forecast objects may be shifted by 200-600 m (for scale 1:50000) from the real position ore mineralization. Presumably

as the scale of geoscanning becomes larger, the forecast areas are more and more localized and shifted to the real position ore mineralization.

The second forecast was made for Russian company “Highland Gold Mining Limited” near gold-silver deposit Belaya Gora. As reference ore mineralization was taken deposit inside of forecasting area. Non-singular mineralization within the most explored sites containing more than # g/t at the depth up to #m and supported by results of heavy mining and drilling works and generally coinciding with contours of commercial mineralization is taken as "ore" standard.

State survey map with 1:50000 scale was used for research.

Gold-silver deposit Belaya Gora located on the left bank of the river Amur in Nikolaevsk region of Khabarovsk krai, in 83 km from Nikolaevsk-na-Amure town.

It located within the lowered tectonic block which limits from north and south latitudinal faults. In centre of block covering volcanites are break through of neck of dacites, trachytes and etc., which was broke of faults northern and north-western direction. Submeridional faults divides neck on west and east extrusions. Belaya Gora deposit spatially and genetically is connected with western extrusion.

Almost all rock in deposit limits hydrothermally are changed from kaolin-sericitic to sericit-quartzose and up to second quartzites and hydrothermal breccias. A rocks which contains ore are metasomatites. Rocks of deposit often are fissural, up to formation crushed zones. A rocks of deposit on majority sectors penetrates small and thin quartzoses, adularia-quartzoses, pyrite-quartzoses streaks.

Ore mineralization is zones of mineralizing explosives breccias, linear stockworks in subvolcanic intrusions, more seldom linear zones of vein-streak mineralization in rocks which contains ore.

Ore mineralization have streak-embedded, cluster character. It is not fixed by any geological indications and clearly defined only on sampling data.

In deposit limits stands out two ore zones: Stockwork and Sloping which breaks up sub latitudinal fault. These are stockworkal deposit which stretches in north-eastern direction and are characterized of uneven gold distribution.

Stockwork ore zone. Maximum vertical ore score – 310 m. In zone limits selected 41 ore bodies. Ore bodies' extension is north-eastern, fall south-eastern. In average falling angles are 30-40°. Ore bodies have very complex morphology and intrinsic structure. Their thickness from 0.5 to 73.7 m. At depth ore bodies gradually wedge out.

Sloping ore zone. It has more simple morphology. In zone limits selected 9 ore bodies. Ore bodies' extension is north-eastern, fall is south-western and fluctuates from 5° to 15°. An ore bodies thickness changes from 0.9 to 26.6 m. Balance reserves of zone are worked out.

Figure 2. The second forecast.

3.1. Forecast results

On ore reference mineralization and forecasting objects very expressed their dependence from latitudinals, submeridianals and north-easterns structures, these objects as if scueezed among faults of these directions.

In all selected 11 forecasting objects – 5 are paramounts (1-5) and 6 are secondary (apparently with poorer mineralization). Specially stand out linear arrangement of objects along submeridianal fault in central part of forecasting area. Reference ore mineralization (projections of ore bodies on horizontal plane) marked of a yellow bubbles concentration.

Object 2 practically completely coincides with well-known deposit. Objects 4 and 5 located in perspective area limits where at present conducting prospecting works. Moreover object 5 coincides with sector carrying out gold-digger's extraction. Object 1 is missed (with this fully agrees the customer) –In former time gold placer was processed here, and practically always on this forecasting area under placer is primary deposit. Well-known deposit on the very north forecasting area geoscanning method non-reveals.

Forecasting objects enough locals. For more detail forecast (including on level of ore bodies) need scale as minimum 1:10000. The points of relief measures (accuracy) arranges every 120 m. In all on area come out more 8500 relief “samples”.

Bubbles concentrations with big size, including on reference ore mineralization (here they are yellow color), shows or on concretes ore bodies, or on sectors with more rich contents.

In general come out what “ore signal” in average correspond to reference deposit (not much big blues and yellows bubbles on diagrams with high significances correspondence to reference ore mineralization). But enough much reds and grins bubbles (not very high level correspondence to reference ore mineralization). Apparently it is connected with considerable unevenness of ore content (Look legend).

When conducting prospecting should be considered that each part of the forecast objects may be shifted by 200-600 m (for scale 1:25000) from the real position ore mineralization. Presumably as the scale of geoscanning becomes larger, the forecast areas are more and more localized and shifted to the real position ore mineralization.

3.2. These examples can be the main conclusions:

- ore signal pattern in auxiliary space was almost identical on, i.e. if we know mineralization of certain contours we can easily and precisely define other contours. Only the last will be as not completely developed photo;
- areas of forecasting mineralization are either completely confirmed by sampling of heavy mine working and drill holes or verification of mineralization was never conducted there.

4. Interpretation

Forecasting layout is well visualized and is easily interpreted when perspective probable sectors are selected under the following categories:

- extracted depth ore signal is divided in values on ranks (similarity) and quantities (approximate ore resources) of correspondence to reference ore mineralization;
- scale effects become well apparent on prognostic layout. Ore field generally forms a zone of higher dispersed mineralization with separate accumulations of ore bodies;
- forecast may be a slightly shifted (up to 500-600 m for geoscanning scale 1:50000-1:25000) from the real position of ore bodies. Presumably as the scale of geoscanning becomes larger, the forecast areas are more and more localized and shifted to the real position ore mineralization;
- bubbles accumulation with high value ore signal more than 9 - 12 (i.e. with size typical for ore bodies of particular ore field) means that mineralization will be commercial with very high (close to 100%) probability level; i.e. bubble accumulation is interpreted as an ore body or deposit and maybe of different configuration depending on morphological type of mineralization. Mineralization in single bubbles with ore signal interpreted as unprofitable. In the others cases the probability of mineralization detection is negligibly small;
- depth of forecast mineralization corresponds to the depth of reference mineralization;
- having additional data characterizing geological structure of the area, criteria for selection of perspective probable sectors are extended and defined more precisely.

5. Conclusion

Method allows selection of perspective areas at the depth with ore formation and parameters similar to standard one.

Obtained prognostic layout of ore mineralization maybe compared with not completely developed photo.

Accuracy of ore signal extraction corresponds to the scale of topographical map, i.e. using a map with 1:10000 scale possibilities of the method allow contouring ore bodies in detail and with high precision. Accuracy of ore signal extraction also depends on precision of contours of reference ore mineralization.

Accuracy of extraction of depth ore signal correspond to scale of topographical map and use map of scales 1:50000-1:25000 means of method makes it possible with sufficient accuracy and precision select deposits, and use map of scales 1:10000-1:2000 – even ore bodies. Accuracy of extraction of depth ore signal depends on precision of outlines and complete of reference ore mineralization too.

Geoscanning method allows operating data of continuous tests in each point of area due to a possibility of measuring relief parameters. A large set of each "sample" will most probably denote mineralization. This is confirmed by the results of exploration works because availability of enormous number of samples (up to dozens of thousands samples per 1 km²) allows contouring ore bodies uniquely.

Method determines unknown hidden and overlapped deposits at any depth. When method works it uses basis .isolines of topographical map without coordinates and outlines and/or points on reference mineralization.

Expected result of our forecast is very high - every 3rd drill hole or mine working will contain ore.

Accuracy of forecast is also very high (up to detection of ore bodies) and decrease exploratory drilling and thus reduces cost and time of operations.

Method discovers unknown hidden resources on deposit flanks. A well-known deposit can be just a small part of an unknown so far large hidden object.

Method can choose better objects and the most perspective, with highest increase of unexplored resources objects from the number of not large and insufficiently explored deposits of the same kind.

Method is quite universal for exploration of different mineral resources.

6. References

Pirnazarov M.M, Ivanov V.N. Application of nontraditional approaches to the forecasting of latent and re-covered gold mineralization (on an example of Chadak). Geology and mineral resources (Uzbekistan), 2001 №3, p. 34-38.